

RNA preservation & RNA extraction protocol suitable for field collection of coral samples

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Summary

The ability to collect samples suitable for RNA extraction in remote field settings is typically hampered by the need for immediate processing or freezing of samples in liquid nitrogen for preservation of nucleic acid integrity. To this end, a range of RNA preservation buffers are available, compatible with ambient temperature transport and subsequent RNA extraction. Here we tested two commonly available RNA storage buffers, RNA*later* from Thermo Fisher Scientific and DNA/RNA Shield from Zymo Research, with subsequent RNA extraction using the RNeasy Mini Kit from Qiagen. We assessed three common coral genera (*Acropora*, *Pocillopora*, *Porites*) reported to yield different levels of RNA quality and quantity, partially due to varying levels of mucus that co-purifies with RNA. All samples were collected in the field and preserved at site (on the boat) with storage at ambient temperature, followed by +4°C and -20°C storage, before subsequent RNA extraction. We found DNA/RNA Shield in combination with the RNeasy Mini Kit to yield non-degraded high quality total RNA. The lytic activity of the DNA/RNA Shield buffer facilitates the separation of the coral tissue from the skeleton. At the same time, minimizing the amount of storage buffer is important to obtain sufficiently concentrated RNA for direct use in downstream applications (e.g., RNA-Seq). In summary, we developed a protocol for coral RNA preservation and RNA extraction suitable for application in remote field settings that yield sufficiently concentrated, high quality RNA for direct use in downstream molecular applications.

Materials & Methods

Sample collection

In December 2021, fragments from adult colonies of *Porites* sp., *Acropora* sp., and *Pocillopora* sp. were collected from Al Fahal reef (22.304909, 38.965029) in the central Red Sea, Saudi Arabia. From each species, fragments for RNA*later* and DNA/RNA Shield from 3 replicate colonies were sampled using a hammer and chisel on SCUBA at depths between 3-8 m. Upon return to the boat, samples were placed in 25 ml tubes and either immersed in RNA*later* (Thermo Fisher Scientific) or DNA/RNA Shield (Zymo Research). All corals were collected under permits from the Saudi Coastguard Authority, issued under the auspices of the King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST).

Sample storage

Upon return to shore, samples were cut into smaller pieces and transferred to 5 ml tubes for long-term storage. The original used storage buffer was re-added to the samples and, after incubation at room temperature for ~2 hours, samples were stored at 4°C for transport to the University of Konstanz, Germany where they were stored at -20°C until processing.

RNA isolation

RNA isolation was performed using the Qiagen RNeasy Mini Kit in combination with the Qiagen QIAcube Connect automated extraction robot. Coral samples were thawed at room temperature and the coral tissue sprayed off using airflow from a sterile 1000 μ l pipette tip connected via a rubber hose to a benchtop air pressure valve.

Coral samples stored in RNA $later$ were removed from the storage tubes with sterile forceps and tapped gently to remove any excess solution. Following this, they were placed into individual sterile whirl-pak bags (Whirl-Pak) and 1000 μ l of the RNeasy Mini Kit RLT buffer added to the fragment. The tissue was then sprayed off using the airflow for a maximum of 3 minutes and collected into the bottom of the whirl-pak bag. The resulting tissue slurry was transferred into a round bottom 2 ml tube and homogenized using a homogenizer (Polytron PT 1200 E, Kinematica) before being centrifuged at full speed for 3 mins. Following this, 300 μ L of the supernatant were transferred into a new round bottom 2 mL tube, and RNA was extracted using the RNeasy Mini Kit with a DNase digestion step following the manufacturer's instructions. Samples were eluted in 50 μ l RNase-free water.

Coral samples stored in DNA/RNA Shield were transferred along with the full volume of the buffer solution into sterile whirl-pak bags, and the fragments were sprayed until all tissue was removed. As evidenced by coloration of the buffer over storage time, part of the coral tissue was already lysed in the storage buffer, due to its lytic activity (Figure S1). The resultant slurry was transferred back into the original 5 ml storage tube and homogenized using a homogenizer (Polytron PT 1200 E, Kinematica). Following this, 300 μ l of homogenized coral tissue were transferred to a 1.5 mL tube and 300 μ l of RNeasy Mini Kit RLT buffer were added with subsequent vortexing, before centrifugation at full speed for 3 mins. The supernatant was transferred into a round bottom 2 mL tube. RNA was extracted using the RNeasy Mini Kit with a DNase digestion step following the manufacturer's instructions. Samples were eluted in 30 μ l RNase-free water.

RNA was quantified using the QIAxcel RNA QC Kit (Qiagen) on the QIAxcel Advanced System (Qiagen). RNA quality was assessed using the Agilent 4150 TapeStation with the RNA ScreenTape assay (Agilent Technologies).

RNA precipitation

Given that the amount of DNA/RNA Shield buffer determines the final RNA concentration of the extraction (as the entirety of the buffer needs to be used due to its inherent lytic activity), we concentrated all RNA extractions using 2.5 volumes of 100% EtOH, 0.1 volumes of 3M sodium acetate pH 5.2, and 1 μ L of glycogen (20 mg/mL) to increase yield (Walker & Lorsch, 2013). This was done to stay within recommended RNA concentrations for the RNA ScreenTape assay (\geq 25 - 500 ng total RNA in 1 μ L). Samples were incubated for at least 2 hours at -80°C. Precipitated RNA was pelleted by centrifugation at 12,000 g for 15 mins at 4°C. The supernatant was removed, the RNA pellet washed with 2.5 volumes of 70% ethanol, air dried for 10 mins at room temperature, and resuspended in 10 μ L of RNase-free water for RNA $later$ samples and in 6 μ L for DNA/RNA Shield samples.

Results

Three species of corals (Table 1) were preserved using two treatments (n = 3 per species per treatment): RNA*later* and DNA/RNA Shield. All samples were then processed using Qiagen's RNeasy Mini Kit.

With regard to RNA quantity, total RNA was obtained from all coral samples, although the relative amounts of extracted total RNA exhibited a genus-/species-specific effect with *Pocillopora* sp. samples yielding highest RNA amounts, followed by *Acropora* sp., followed by *Porites* sp., irrespective of the storage buffer used (Table 1).

With regard to RNA quality, samples preserved in DNA/RNA Shield yielded consistently non-degraded RNA, as denoted by the sharp 18S and 28S RNA peaks and also consistently higher RIN values, in comparison to samples preserved in RNA*later* (Figure 1).

Discussion

The genomic revolution has made the molecular analysis of large cohorts of field samples feasible, both in terms of processing and cost (Ungerer, Johnson, & Herman, 2008). This necessitates the need for sample preservation in remote field settings, either for DNA- or RNA-based applications (Gray, Pratte, & Kellogg, 2013; Voolstra, Quigley, et al., 2021). In particular, RNA is very unstable at room temperature and degrades in less than an hour. A range of RNA preservation buffers are now available that are compatible with ambient temperature storage and transport. Here we assessed RNA*later* (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and DNA/RNA Shield (Zymo Research), two commonly available RNA storage buffers, for their suitability for coral RNA preservation using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen).

For the three tested species (*Pocillopora* sp., *Porites* sp., *Acropora* sp.), DNA/RNA Shield yielded largely undegraded, intact total RNA, as evidenced by the presence of clear and distinct 18S and 28S rRNA bands. Also, RIN numbers were consistently higher for DNA/RNA Shield preserved specimens. Of note, the lytic activity of the DNA/RNA Shield buffer necessitates that the entire storage buffer volume and the preserved specimen need to be considered for RNA extraction, as already lysed cells in the buffer solution will otherwise be unaccounted. Therefore, it is important to minimize storage buffer volume in order to achieve the total RNA concentrations required for subsequent molecular applications. For our samples, *Pocillopora* and *Acropora* yielded sufficiently highly concentrated total RNA for direct downstream application. However, *Porites* sp. is known to harbor high amounts of mucus that interferes with nucleic acid isolations and typically results in low yields (Bouchard, Michaels, & Brown-Harding, 2020; Robbins et al., 2019). This was confirmed for our samples and irrespective of the preservation buffer used (Table 1).

To increase total RNA concentrations, samples were hence precipitated to achieve concentrations recommended for the TapeStation System. As evident from Table 1 and Figure 1, this only worked for some of the *Porites* sp. samples (in the other cases the precipitated pellet might have been lost resulting in loss of RNA). As such, this added complication should be

avoided if possible. We have found that storing samples in plastic bags (e.g., Whirl Paks) allows the use of very low volumes of storage buffer (~2-3 mL) to achieve higher total RNA concentrations. Plastic bags also accommodate the fact that coral fragments typically come in shapes and sizes that makes them challenging to fit in a 25ml- or 50ml-conical tube opening (Figure S2).

Of additional note, spraying off tissue from the underlying coral skeleton is typically not an easy endeavor and requires significant amounts of time and should typically be conducted under a hooded area or while wearing a face mask and safety goggles, due to the allergic properties of coral tissue (Miguel-Gomez & Fonda-Pascual, 2016). We have found that spraying off tissue from fragments immersed in DNA/RNA Shield works much better in that the tissue and polyps typically detach very easily from the underlying skeleton (Figure S3), which saves processing and minimizes exposure time.

At large, the development of standardized protocols and procedures facilitates the comparison of experimental and field data (meta-analyses) (Grottoli et al., 2021; Voolstra, Suggett, et al., 2021), in particular for gene expression-based comparisons that were shown to be affected by sample collection procedure and RNA isolation method (Asare et al., 2008; Scholes & Lewis, 2020). Prompted by the large meta-analysis of expression data as part of the Paul G. Allen Family Foundation Project “Search for corals with natural resilience to climate change” (aka “Global Search”) ([link](#), [link](#)) using the Coral Bleaching Automated Stress System (CBASS) (Voolstra et al., 2020) with subsequent molecular analyses (Voolstra, Valenzuela, et al., 2021), we here developed a protocol for RNA isolation that is compatible with collection of samples in remote field settings that we hope can be applied and will be used widely.

Table 1. Overview of samples and RNA extraction methods and yields. Abbreviations: Poc = *Pocillopora* sp., Acr = *Acropora* sp., Por = *Porites* sp.; Rep. = Replicate; RIN = RNA Integrity Number

Species	Rep.	Storage Buffer	Input/amount used for RNA extraction	Elution volume [μl]	Conc. [ng/μl]	Conc. after precipitation [ng/μl]	Total RNA amount [ng]	RIN
Poc	1			50	169.84	2112.57	21,125.70	5.0
Poc	2	RNA/later	Sprayed off tissue in 1000 μl RLT; used 350 μl for RNA extraction	50	271.04	2592.95	25,929.50	4.9
Poc	3			50	278.25	2492.19	24,921.90	-
Por	1			50	2.85	192.89	1,928.90	2.8
Por	2	RNA/later	Sprayed off tissue in 1000 μl RLT; used 350 μl for RNA extraction	50	2.97	45.00	450.00	2.5
Por	3			50	0.32	9.45	94.50	-
Acr	1			50	76.22	1151.87	11,518.70	3.5
Acr	2	RNA/later	Sprayed off tissue in 1000 μl RLT; used 350 μl for RNA extraction	50	107.20	1252.85	12,528.50	5.1
Acr	3			N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Poc	1			Sprayed off tissue using initial volume of 5ml	30	153.84	467.48	2,804.88
Poc	2	DNA/RNA Shield	DNA/RNA Shield; used 300 ul of DNA/RNA Shield + 300 ul RLT buffer for RNA extraction	30	266.94	706.44	4,238.64	7.1
Poc	3			30	535.50	406.00	2,436.00	6.6
Por	1			Sprayed off tissue using initial volume of 5ml	30	7.27	3.00	18.00
Por	2	DNA/RNA Shield	DNA/RNA Shield; used 300 ul of DNA/RNA Shield + 300 ul RLT buffer for RNA extraction	30	18.21	44.88	269.28	7.5
Por	3			30	1.34	4.53	27.18	-
Acr	1			Sprayed off tissue using initial volume of 5ml	30	88.06	23.10	138.60
Acr	2	DNA/RNA Shield	DNA/RNA Shield; used 300 ul of DNA/RNA Shield + 300 ul RLT buffer for RNA extraction	30	53.12	61.58	369.48	7.1
Acr	3			30	18.12	85.84	515.04	5.3

Figure 1. Total RNA profiles of selected samples (refer to Table 1 for sample details) run on an Agilent TapeStation. In all cases DNA/RNA Shield samples exhibit distinct 18S and 28S rRNA bands, indicative of no/minor RNA degradation. For 3 of the *Porites* sp. samples (Por3 RNA later, Por1 DNA/RNA Shield, Por3 DNA/RNA Shield), the concentrations were below recommended concentrations (at least 25ng/ μ L).

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. *Porites* sp. fragment in RNA/later (left) and DNA/RNA Shield (right), illustrating the lytic activity of the DNA/RNA Shield buffer as illustrated by the brownish color of the buffer.

Figure S2. Coral samples immersed in DNA/RNA Shield buffer in a zip-tied Whirl-Pak bag. The buffer shows coloration indicating the ongoing tissue lysis, which considerably facilitates spraying off the tissue from the skeleton.

Figure S3. Coral tissue and polyps typically detach easily from the underlying skeleton when spraying off fragments that were stored in DNA/RNA Shield buffer. Shown is the coral fragment on the left, the 1000 μ l pipette tip connected to a benchtop air pressure valve on the top right, and the sprayed off polyps and tissue in DNA/RNA Shield buffer in the bottom right of the Whirl-Pak bag. The detached, sprayed-off polyps look similar to chia seeds.

Protocol (step-by-step): DNA/RNA Shield buffer-based sample collection, storage, and processing for RNA isolation of coral field samples

Resources/Read *before* you start

- [DNA/RNA Shield](#)
- [RNeasy Mini Handbook](#)

Coral sample collection

1. Collect branching coral species (e.g., *Acropora* sp.) with hammer and chisel or clippers, collect massive coral species (e.g., *Porites* sp.) with underwater drill and core drill bit (e.g., [link](#))
2. Place specimens into collection bags, make sure the bags are filled with seawater.
3. Upon return to the boat/shore place the sample bags inside a cooler box filled with seawater until further processing.

DNA/RNA Shield buffer-based coral sample storage

1. Transfer coral samples to whirl-pak bags (e.g., [link](#)) and add 2-3 mL of DNA/RNA Shield buffer (use the minimum amount of buffer to cover the sample in order to maximize RNA concentration).
2. Use a (reusable) cable tie to seal the whirl-pak bag so that the coral fragment is secured and fully submerged in the DNA/RNA Shield buffer (Figure S2).
3. Store at RT/4°C/-20°C until further processing (colder temperatures increase storage time: 35 - 40°C ≤ 7 days; 4°C - 25°C ≥ 30 days; ≤ -20°C = indefinite)

Coral sample processing

1. Spray off coral tissue into the storage whirl-pak bag filled with DNA/RNA Shield using airflow from a sterile 1000 µL pipette filter-tip connected via a rubber hose to a bench top air pressure valve or an airbrush compressor set, until all of the coral tissue is removed from the skeleton (Figure S3).
2. Transfer tissue slurry with accompanying DNA/RNA Shield buffer into a screw-cap cryogenic viable and store at RT/4°C/-20°C until further processing.

Coral RNA isolation using the RNeasy Mini Kit

1. If applicable: defrost samples at room temperature.
2. Homogenize the tissue slurry with a homogenizer (e.g., Polytron PT 1200 E with a 3 mm dispersing aggregate, e.g. [link](#))

NOTE: incomplete homogenization leads to significantly reduced RNA yields and can cause clogging of the RNeasy Mini kit spin column. Recommended minimum speed using disperser above is ~70% of max.

NOTE: We use the RNeasy Mini Kit ([link](#)) and follow procedures based on the “Protocol: Purification of Total RNA from Animal Tissues” and the “Optional On-Column DNase Digestion with the RNase-Free DNase Set” (Appendix D)

NOTE: Read ‘Important points before starting’ in the RNeasy Mini Handbook.

Alternative 1:

3. Vortex and transfer 300 μ L of the 2 mL tissue slurry into a 1.5 mL tube (store the remaining slurry at -20°C).
4. Add 300 μ L of RNeasy Mini Kit RLT buffer to the slurry and vortex.

Alternative 2:

NOTE: In the course of RNA extractions with different coral species, we found in some cases it is better to pellet the homogenized tissue slurry in DNA/RNA Shield buffer and only use 300 μ L of the supernatant for subsequent RNA isolations. Since the DNA/RNA Shield buffer is lytic and the coral tissue is homogenized, this effectively spins down cell debris and other tissue entities that may interfere with downstream RNA isolation

3. Spin homogenized coral tissue in DNA/RNA Shield buffer for 3 min at max speed; transfer 300 μ L of supernatant into a 1.5 mL tube; be careful not to disturb the pellet (store the remaining slurry at -20°C).
4. Add 300 μ L of RNeasy Mini Kit RLT buffer to the slurry and vortex.

NOTE: We do not add β -Mercaptoethanol to Buffer RLT

NOTE: DNA/RNA Shield buffer provides protection against multiple freeze-thaw cycles.

5. Centrifuge at max speed for 3 mins at RT.
6. Transfer 600 μ L of supernatant (lysate) into a new 2 mL round bottom tube; avoid disturbing the pellet.
7. Add 1 volume of 70% ethanol to the lysate and mix well by pipetting. Do not centrifuge. Proceed immediately to the next step.
8. Transfer up to 700 μ L of the sample, including any precipitate, to an RNeasy spin column placed in a 2 mL collection tube. Centrifuge for 15 sec at $\geq 8000 \times g$ at RT. Discard the flow-through.
9. Transfer the remaining volume of the sample to the *same* RNeasy spin column placed in the 2 mL collection tube. Centrifuge for 15 sec at $\geq 8000 \times g$ at RT. Discard the flow-through.

NOTE: Using the entirety of the sample increases RNA yield.

NOTE: Perform all centrifugation steps at 20 – 25°C in a standard microcentrifuge. Ensure that the centrifuge does not cool below 20°C .

10. Add 350 μ L Buffer RW1 to the RNeasy spin column. Centrifuge for 15 sec at $\geq 8000 \times g$ at RT. Discard the flow-through.
11. Add 10 μ L DNase I stock solution to 70 μ L Buffer RDD. Mix by gently inverting the tube. Centrifuge briefly.

12. Add the DNase I incubation mix (80 μ L) directly to the RNeasy spin column membrane, incubate at RT for 15 min.

NOTE: The DNase set needs to be purchased separately ([link](#)); standard DNase buffers are not compatible with on-column DNase digestion.

NOTE: We have found that the DNase step is important to correctly estimate RNA concentration; typically, in samples with low RNA yield, DNA is isolated more effectively; thus, without DNase digestions RNA yields are hard to accurately determine (in the case of photometric determination; not so much of an issue for fluorescence-based determination with RNA-specific dyes)

13. Add 350 μ L Buffer RW1 to the RNeasy spin column. Centrifuge for 15 sec at $\geq 8000 \times g$ at RT. Discard the flow-through.
14. Add 500 μ L Buffer RPE to the RNeasy spin column. Centrifuge for 15 sec at $\geq 8000 \times g$ at RT. Discard the flow-through.
15. Add 500 μ L Buffer RPE to the RNeasy spin column. Centrifuge for 2 min at $\geq 8000 \times g$ at RT.
16. Place the RNeasy spin column in a new 2 mL collection tube. Centrifuge at full speed for 1 min to dry the membrane.
17. Place the RNeasy spin column in a new 1.5 mL tube. Add 30 μ L RNase-free water directly to the spin column membrane. Centrifuge for 1 min at $\geq 8000 \times g$ at RT to elute the RNA.
18. Assess RNA quantity and quality; store at -80°C in RNase-free water.

NOTE: Electrophoresis-based quality (e.g., BioAnalyzer or QIAxcel) and fluorescent dye-based quantity assessment (e.g., Qubit) are ideal, but 'classical' gel electrophoresis to check for presence/integrity of 18S/28S bands and photometric concentration assessment (e.g., NanoDrop) work just fine to assess success of RNA isolation.

References

- Asare, A. L., Kolchinsky, S. A., Gao, Z., Wang, R., Raddassi, K., Bourcier, K., & Seyfert-Margolis, V. (2008). Differential gene expression profiles are dependent upon method of peripheral blood collection and RNA isolation. *BMC Genomics*, 9, 474. doi: 10.1186/1471-2164-9-474
- Bouchard, C., Michaels, J., & Brown-Harding, H. (2020). RNA isolation from corals and other cnidarian species using urea-LiCl as a denaturant. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 588, 113472. doi: 10.1016/j.ab.2019.113472
- Gray, M. A., Pratte, Z. A., & Kellogg, C. A. (2013). Comparison of DNA preservation methods for environmental bacterial community samples. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 83(2), 468–477. doi: 10.1111/1574-6941.12008
- Grottoli, A. G., Toonen, R. J., van Woosik, R., Vega Thurber, R., Warner, M. E., McLachlan, R. H., ... Wu, H. C. (2021). Increasing comparability among coral bleaching experiments. *Ecological Applications: A Publication of the Ecological Society of America*, 31(4), e02262. doi: 10.1002/eap.2262
- Miguel-Gomez, L., & Fonda-Pascual, P. (2016). Acute coral contact dermatitis. *CMAJ: Canadian Medical Association Journal = Journal de l'Association Médicale Canadienne*, 188(17-18), 1260. doi: 10.1503/cmaj.151370
- Robbins, S. J., Singleton, C. M., Chan, C. X., Messer, L. F., Geers, A. U., Ying, H., ... Bourne, D. G. (2019). A genomic view of the reef-building coral *Porites lutea* and its microbial symbionts. *Nature Microbiology*, 4(12), 2090–2100. doi: 10.1038/s41564-019-0532-4
- Scholes, A. N., & Lewis, J. A. (2020). Comparison of RNA isolation methods on RNA-Seq: implications for differential expression and meta-analyses. *BMC Genomics*, 21(1), 249. doi: 10.1186/s12864-020-6673-2
- Ungerer, M. C., Johnson, L. C., & Herman, M. A. (2008). Ecological genomics: understanding gene and genome function in the natural environment. *Heredity*, 100(2), 178–183. doi: 10.1038/sj.hdy.6800992
- Voolstra, C. R., Buitrago-López, C., Perna, G., Cárdenas, A., Hume, B. C. C., Rådecker, N., & Barshis, D. J. (2020). Standardized short-term acute heat stress assays resolve historical differences in coral thermotolerance across microhabitat reef sites. *Global Change Biology*, 26(8), 4328–4343. doi: 10.1111/gcb.15148
- Voolstra, C. R., Quigley, K. M., Davies, S. W., Parkinson, J. E., Peixoto, R. S., Aranda, M., ... Sweet, M. (2021). Consensus guidelines for advancing coral holobiont genome and specimen voucher deposition. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 1029. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2021.701784
- Voolstra, C. R., Suggett, D. J., Peixoto, R. S., Parkinson, J. E., Quigley, K. M., Silveira, C. B., ... Aranda, M. (2021). Extending the natural adaptive capacity of coral holobionts. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 2(11), 747–762. doi: 10.1038/s43017-021-00214-3
- Voolstra, C. R., Valenzuela, J. J., Turkarslan, S., Cárdenas, A., Hume, B. C. C., Perna, G., ... Barshis, D. J. (2021). Contrasting heat stress response patterns of coral holobionts across the Red Sea suggest distinct mechanisms of thermal tolerance. *Molecular Ecology*, 30(18), 4466–4480. doi: 10.1111/mec.16064
- Walker, S. E., & Lorsch, J. (2013). Chapter Nineteen - RNA Purification – Precipitation Methods. In J. Lorsch (Ed.), *Methods in Enzymology* (Vol. 530, pp. 337–343). Academic Press. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-420037-1.00019-1